

Determination of cosmological constant and Hubble constant from e-dimensionality

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ABSTRACT: The issues encircling the cosmological constant and Hubble constant paradox is analyzed from the telescopic view of a novel proposal by Kak called the e-dimensional universe. Salient features of the theory are laid out and some of the limitations are expounded as well. The paper is closed with a short discussion of the modern methods to resolve these issues as well as the exposition of possible insights and links that might be missing in considering these problems.

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1 Introduction

The current theories and models of the standard model are facing a hard time accounting for the estimates of the Hubble parameter and the nature of the cosmological constant. For the former, several probes and collaborations have obtained contrasting and conflicting values in the early universe and late universe case respectively, for instance the Planck collaboration [1], the Hubble telescope [2], Chandra observatory [3] and recently the measurements have been obtained by the LIGO/VIRGO collaboration following the GW190521 event [4]. The measurements obtained from several projects indicate that the Hubble constant doesn't behave like a constant given the varying values obtained by the probes. Recent projects such as the James Webb Telescope might be able to shed more light on the paradox.

Several theories and models exist for the latter as well but none has been able to satisfactorily answer the true nature of the cosmological constant which many believe to be the dark energy, a agent responsible for the accelerating expansion of the universe [5, 6, 7, 8].

With the motivation to get a bit closer to answering some of these questions, Kak has proposed a theory called the e-dimensional universe according to which the universe is not 3-dimensional as described by Euclidean geometry but e-dimensional i.e. of non-integer dimensionality [9, 10]. We review aspects of this theory momentarily in the next section.

2 A brief review of e-dimensional universe

The theory starts from the hypothesis that physical space is e-dimensional (where $e = 2.71828\dots$). Kak argues that the notion of assigning a 3-dimensional structure to our universe is just a matter of convention and in reality it might not be the case. The author has also explained his theory for the laymen [11]. The author has expressed that an e-dimensional object would look something like a sponge or cheese. Kak on the basis of his theory has also explained the asymptotic freedom [12] and argues that it explains gravity and the dynamics of the universe [13]. In the latter paper he has specifically sought a non-integer dimensional explanation for inflation, the accelerating expansion of the universe etc without trying to incorporate the inflaton or dark energy (as agents driving the inflation and expansion) into the picture. The theory is supposedly consistent with the standard cosmology and assumes the Minkowski metric for the flat expanding universe while preserving the cosmological principle of homogeneity and isotropy. The author expresses a potential $p(d, r)$ as a function of the dimensionality d of the space and function f relating the difference between the actual dimension of the space and its ceiling integer value which has the form,

$$p(d, r) = \begin{cases} \frac{f(2-d)}{4\pi} & , 1 \leq d \leq 2 \\ \frac{f(3-d)}{4\pi r d} & , 2 \leq d \leq 3 \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

Following this line, the variation of the Newton's gravitational constant with changing dimensions is explored and the gravitational constant is obtained as the functional form,

$$G(d, t) = G(d) = \begin{cases} G_0(5d - d^2 - 6) & ; d \leq e \\ 0.202 G_0 & ; d > e \end{cases} \quad (2.2)$$

The equation for the expansion rate is also found and is given by,

$$V(t) - V_g(t) = V_0 e^{-\alpha t} - G(t) \quad (2.3)$$

One of the most important aspects of Kak's proposal is the description of different evolutionary stages of the universe with varying time and dimensions on the basis of e-dimensionality. He writes [13],

"From its initial point singularity, the universe must increase its dimensionality in stages. First, the initial dimensionality potential transforms into radiation and subsequently to matter. This means that it must first become filaments ($d = 1$) or line fractals that are one-dimensional scale-invariant structures and then sheets ($d = 2$) before transforming into matter as the dimensionality increases beyond 2. One may speculate that the filaments consisted of neutrinos and photons came later. As the dimensionality becomes greater than 2, there will be an exponential rise over the values $2 \leq d \leq e$. Beyond 2, the inverse square law arises and by Occam's Razor we may take it to be gravitation."

The evolutionary epochs as described in the original paper are summarized below.

**Epoch 1: Filaments*— $0 \leq d \leq 1$: This epoch is marked by one-dimensional fractal filaments with optimal value reaching to $e/3$.

**Epoch 2: Inflationary expansion*— $1 \leq d \leq 2$: In this constraint, fractal sheets will rise to $2e/3$. The radiation would undergo a scale-invariant distribution over the sheet and additional forces may also be associated within this constraint. The expansion would be close to instantaneous.

**Epoch 3: Radiation to matter*— $2 \leq d \leq d_{critical}$ (slowing expansion): As the dimensionality becomes greater than 2, the inverse square law comes into the picture which may be regarded as gravitation, taking into account the concept of Occam's Razor. The attractive force increases for $2 \leq d \leq d_{critical}$ and thus there will be slowing down of the expansion over this domain because matter is pulled towards each other with increasing value. This further is resolved into two sub-epochs: one in which the radiation dominates, and the other in which matter dominates. After $d_{critical}$, that appears to occur somewhere in the middle of 2 and 3 (2.5 is taken to be precise) the gravitational attraction decreases and as a consequence the expansion rate will increase.

**Epoch 4: Accelerating expansion*— $d_{critical} \leq d \leq e$: A much slower yet gradual expansion of space continued after this, until at around 9.8 billion years (4 billion years ago) when it began to expand rigorously, and maintains the same to this day. The author doesn't regard this as the work of dark energy enveloped as the cosmological constant and explains the anomalies using the implications of e-dimensionality.

**Epoch 5: The future*— $d = e$ (decreasing V): This would lead first to decelerating expansion and consequently to big crunch.

One major advantage of this theory is its practicality over SUSY models and string-theoretic explanations. Where the explanations based on the latter are far from being empirically testable, the former has implications which are comparatively easier to test and realised.

3 Hubble parameter from e-dimensionality

Kak in his original paper, uses data from the Planck Collaboration for the early universe estimate of the Hubble constant which has value $67 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ and SHoES (Supernova H_o for the Equation of State) for the corresponding late universe estimate with the magnitude $74 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$.

Figure 1. The redshift-distance relationship for distant galaxies. The points that don't fall exactly on the line owe the slight mismatch to the differences in peculiar velocities, which offer only slight deviations from the overall observed expansion. The original data from Edwin Hubble, first used to show the Universe was expanding, all fit in the small red box at the lower-left. [Credits: ROBERT KIRSHNER, PNAS, 101, 1, 8-13 (2004)]

Kak resolves the discrepancy between the two estimates on the basis of e-dimensionality. He writes [10],

"We now present a resolution to the problem of the diverging estimates of the Hubble constant H_0 , based on early- or late- universe models. The discrepancy is between the values of $67 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ from the early universe and $74 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ from the late universe. This resolution comes from our information-theoretic perspective that implies that the optimal dimension to be associated with physical space is $e = 2.71828$. If physical reality is e-dimensional and we insist on viewing it as being 3-dimensional then there is a discrepancy equal to $e/3 = 0.9060$. This number is very close to the divergence of $67/74 = 0.9054$ from the experimental data.

The efficiency of the three-dimensional space is of from the e-dimensional optimal space by about 0.003, or about 0.6 percent. One may speculate that since our cognitions are based on counting, we associate the nearest integer space of 3 dimensions to space which leads to our normal sense about its nature."

Despite the strong agreement between the data and theoretical prediction (from e-dimensionality), there are limitations. Apart from the Planck collaboration and SHoES

data, e-dimensionality is not in close agreement with the values of the Hubble constant obtained by other probes and experiments. Also, e-dimensionality doesn't explain why Hubble constant is fluctuating in nature. These are some points of concern which are left to be explored.

4 Cosmological constant: real or fictitious?

The cosmological constant showed up first in Einstein's field equation in general relativity which he called the greatest mistake of his life [14, 15]. Einstein's equation with the cosmological constant reads,

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu} \quad (4.1)$$

where $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci tensor, R is the Ricci scalar, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, G is Newton's constant and $T_{\mu\nu}$ is the energy-momentum tensor. One can have a look at a number of literature for getting acquainted with the status of the cosmological constant, see for example [16, 17]. The cosmological constant is widely accepted as the simplest explanation for dark energy and is incorporated into the standard model of cosmology which is the Λ CDM model [18]. In spite of being a central tenet of modern cosmology, it is not yet clear as to what this really corresponds to and the discrepancy between the theoretical calculation from QFT and observational constraints is so large that it is one of the most well known problems of science today.

One can get an idea of the magnitude of the cosmological constant from the data as collected by the Supernovae Cosmology Project and the High-Z Supernova Team, both of which reported the same small but, nevertheless, nonzero and positive value given by,

$$\Lambda \approx 10^{-52} m^{-2} \approx 10^{-35} s^{-2} \quad (4.2)$$

Physicists have proposed innumerable methods and theories in order to tackle the cosmological constant problem ranging from anthropic arguments [19, 20], string theory landscape [21, 22], modified gravity theories [23, 24, 25, 26] and other approaches [27, 28, 29]. However no consensus has been reached as yet.

In the e-dimensional theory, there is no room for the cosmological constant or dark energy and the issues associated with these are resolved using methods employed by the e-dimensionality hypothesis. Quoting [13],

"Our model shows that there is no need to postulate dark energy as being responsible for the accelerated expansion, for in our theory it was a consequence of the weakening of the attractive gravitational force as compared to the dimension-driven energy responsible for the expansion of the universe."

As we saw, there are a wide number of approaches and theories which are trying to argue in favour of cosmological constant or dark energy and there are also those which are doing the opposite, for instance the theory under consideration in this paper. Today the predominant issue is that everyone is trying to provide his/her own explanation of natural

phenomena rather than actually seeking the true nature behind them. Only time will tell which of the theories are close enough to reality so that it can be incorporated and which are far from reality and just our "thought" on how nature behaves rather than how nature "actually" is and hence can be discarded.

5 Future prospects

We got accustomed with the fundamentals of the e-dimensionality theory and also saw how it tackles some of the major issues in modern cosmology today. Although the theory throws a new light on the problem and provides a new method to resolve them, the problems are yet to be fully accomplished and it will not be so unless we have some significant empirical evidence in favour of the theory as considered in this paper. Nevertheless we can talk a bit about some future prospects on the problems studied here.

Supersymmetry is widely explored in order to settle the cosmological constant problem. However, as we discussed earlier, supersymmetry is impractical as of now and is inconsistent with our low-energy world. If there is a supersymmetry, the positive contribution of bosons and negative contribution of fermions exactly cancel each other. However, it is well known that there is no supersymmetry in our low-energy world. This means that there must be an energy scale E_{SUSY} below which the supersymmetry is violated and thus there is no balance between bosons and fermions in the vacuum energy [30].

Volovik in his book suggests a method to resolve the problem. He writes [30],

"One possible way to solve this contradiction is to accept that the theoretical criteria for setting the absolute zero point of energy are unclear within the effective theory, i.e. the vacuum energy is by no means the energy of vacuum fluctuations of effective fields. Its estimation requires physics beyond the Planck scale and thus beyond general relativity."

He further adds and explicitly shows that trans-Planckian physics solves the cosmological constant problems in quantum liquids.

Ultimately it may also turn out that there are issues right at the foundations of standard physics and we might be overlooking some principal characteristics of cosmological constant and the Hubble constant. Unless we clear with the true nature behind these phenomena or for that matter, have a fully fledged quantum gravity framework or the theory of everything, these issues might not get to their ultimate settlement.

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